

Duration of dormancy of varieties released by APAU, India.

Variety with indicated dormancy					
1 wk	2 wk	3 wk	4 wk	5 wk	6 wk
Puskala	Sowbhagya	Dhanya	Gowthami	Vasista	Gutti Akkulu
Hamsa	Prathibha	Lakshmi	Chaitanya	Kotha-	Kothamolokolukulu 72
Tella-Hamsa	Sona	Kakatiya	Vajram	Bayahunda	Kothamolokolukulu 74
	Mahsuri	Vamsi	Mahendra		
Rajendra	Pothana	Prabhath	Krishnaveni		Pinakini
Sathya	Saleema	Vijaya-Mahsuri			Tikkana
Badva		Nagavali			
Mahsuri		Lakshmi			
Mahsuri		Surekha			
		Samba -			
		Mahsuri			
		Swarna			

for 80% germination) was estimated by germination percentage.

Germination was tested weekly starting 1 wk after harvest, by sowing 100 seeds of each variety on a petri dish with four replications. Samples were maintained at a constant 30°C.

In general, long-duration varieties had longer seed dormancy (4-6 wk) than medium-duration varieties (2-3 wk) and short-duration varieties (1-2 wk) (see table). Exceptions are some long-duration varieties (Badva Mahsuri, Mahsuri, Sowbhagya, Prathibha, and Sona Mahsuri) that exhibited shorter dormancy (1-2 wk). ■

Effect of variety, nitrogen, and stubble height on ratoon rice yield

R. Balasubramanian and A. Mohamed Ali, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Killikulam 627252, Tamil Nadu, India

Short-duration varieties ADT36, ASD16, and ADT37; N (75, 100, and 125 kg/ha), and 20- and 30-cm stubble height were tested in a split-plot design with three replications. The main crop followed recommended practices.

ADT37 had the highest ratoon crop grain yield, straw yield, and productive tillers and highest daily productivity (see table).

Nitrogen at 125 kg/ha gave significantly higher grain yield, straw yield,

Effect of variety, nitrogen, and stubble height on ratoon rice yield.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Days to maturity (no.)	Productivity (kg/d)
ADT36	2.5	2.5	8.7	77.4	32.3
ADT37	2.8	2.6	10.2	76.5	36.6
ASD16	2.2	2.3	8.5	89.4	24.6
LSD	0.1	0.1	1.2	2.3	-
75 kg N/ha	2.4	2.4	8.8	80.2	29.9
100 kg N/ha	2.5	2.5	9.1	81.1	30.8
125 kg N/ha	2.7	2.5	9.4	82.1	32.9
LSD (0.5)	0.1	0.1	ns	2.3	-
20-cm stubble	2.5	2.4	9.2	81.3	30.8
30-cm stubble	2.5	2.5	9.1	80.9	30.9
LSD	ns	ns	ns	ns	-

and daily productivity than 75 kg N/ha.

Stubble height had no effect on ratoon yields and productive tillers.

The high grain yield in ADT37 could be due to greater number of productive tillers. ■

Pest resistance — diseases

Resistance of some rice varieties to sheath blight (ShB)

Xue-Yan Sha and Li-Hong Zhu, Nanjing Agricultural University, Nanjing 210014, China

ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* is an increasingly serious disease of rice in the Yangtze River Basin, especially hybrid rice. In the search for resistance genes to transfer into commercial

Reaction ^a of varieties to ShB during 1987-89 in China.

Cultivar	Disease ratings (mean and SD) ^b			Average ^a
	1987	1988	1989	
Ta-poo-cho-z	1.43±0.389	0.46±0.190	1.35±0.293	1.08 a
Tetep	2.05±0.315	0.57±0.157	1.65±0.245	1.19 a
Guyanal	1.19±0.304	1.72±0.198	1.93±0.305	1.61 a
IET4699	2.47±0.249	0.49±0.153	2.53±0.233	1.72 ab
Ratna	1.92±0.283	0.98±0.222	2.58±0.287	1.83 ab
Jawa no. 14	2.51±0.214	0.74±0.153	2.50±0.292	1.93 ab
IR64	2.47±0.294	1.01±0.282	2.35±0.201	1.94 ab
Kataktara Da-2	2.9 ±0.206	0.96±0.240	2.51±0.180	2.12 ab
Mian-Hua-Tiao	2.96±0.227	1.58±0.218	2.90±0.200	2.48 ab
Ye-Dao	2.91±0.224	1.90±0.255	3.15±0.275	2.65 ab
P5275	2.85±0.304	2.16±0.335	3.01±0.401	2.67 ab
Nampungbyeo	2.78±0.316	2.15±0.279	3.21±0.248	2.71 ab
IR9752-71-3-2	4.24±0.411	3.76±0.327	4.56±0.309	4.22 b

^a 0 = no lesion, 5 = lesions extend to top sheath. ^b Mean of 10 random hills/treatment with 2 replications. ^c Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by new Duncan's multiple range test at the 1% level.

varieties, we field-tested 12 resistant varieties and susceptible IR9752-71-3-2. We examined disease variation within year and interaction between year and variety during May-Oct 1987-89 in a randomized complete block design with two replications. Plants

were inoculated by stem-tape-inoculation method at maximum tillering and evaluated 2 wk later on 0-5 scale.

The results show differences among the tested varieties, although the differences varied from year to year. Tetep, Ta-poo-cho-z, and Guyanal

were best resistance donors in this test (see table).

Because the interaction between variety and year was highly significant, data for several years are essential in screening. ■

Pest resistance — insects

Resistance in rice to gall midge (GM) under natural conditions

C. R. Elsy, C. A. Rosamma, and N. R. Nair, Regional Agricultural Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India

We evaluated 16 medium-tall rice varieties from the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, during 1989 wet season to identify donors of resistance to rice GM and leafhopper (LF). Entries were planted in 13 rows at 10- × 15-cm spacing with three replications. Pest infestation was scored at 40 d after transplanting.

LF incidence was low during the season. GM infestation varied greatly among the entries (see table). Damage to the susceptible check exceeded the minimum threshold score of 3.

Resistance of rice cultivars to GM. Pattamhi, Kerala, India.

Designation	Cross	Mean score ^a	Average yield (t/ha)
RP2432-85-3-1	IR36/IET7916	0	2.3
R320-298	Samridhi/IR36	2	2.9
RP1579-1633-55-4-3	Phalguna/ARCC6650	2	1.5
UP2431-6-6-2	IR36/IET7918	3	2.2
RP2199-104-64-18-1	Phalguna/TKH6	3	0.85
RP1579-1633-55-43	6-17/ARC6650	4	1.4
RP2439-22-3-3	IR50/IET7918	4	2.2
RP1506-2709-688	TN1/ARC147668	5	2.6
RP2439-22-3-3	IR50/IET7918	5	1.7
HKR119	IR36/IET7916	5	2.3
Ratna		5	2.3
RP1990-979-1097-2	Sona/ARC14528	6	2.1
R296-471-2	CRI57-329/OR67-21	6	1.6
R321-43	Samridhi/IR36	6	2.8
R321-49	Samridhi/IR36	6	2.5
Sasyasree		6	1.1
LSD (P = 0.0.5)			0.5

^a By the Standard evaluation system for rice scale

RP2432-85-3-1 exhibited a high degree of resistance in all three replications. Susceptible checks Ratna and Sadyasree scored 5 and 6, respectively. R320-298 had the highest yield. The average yield

of RP2432-85-3-1 was comparable. The two cultivars could be used as donors of GM resistance and for commercial cultivation in endemic areas. ■

Reactions of rice varieties to rice moth *Sitotroga cerealella*

W. A. Gillani and M. Irshad, National Agricultural Research Center, Islamabad, Pakistan

We studied eight rice varieties in the laboratory for resistance to Angoumois grain moth *S. cerealella* (Oliv.).

Adult moths from a laboratory culture reared at 29 ± 2 °C and 65 ± 5% relative humidity were released in small glass jars for egg laying. Two hundred 24-h-old eggs were placed on 30 g of rice in glass jars, in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Hatched and unhatched eggs were counted 1 wk later.

Adults started emerging after 25 d. Loss in grain weight was considered an

index of susceptibility. Damaged grains were also determined.

Dry weight loss in all rices except KS282 and DR82 differed significantly, (see table). JP5 was most susceptible and DR82 least susceptible to *S. cerealella* attack. DR82, KS282, and Lateefy seem suitable for storage. A strong

positive correlation existed between number of adults that emerged and weight loss ($r = 0.93$), number of adults that emerged and grain damage ($r = 0.92$), and percent damaged grains and percent weight loss ($r = 0.98$).

These results conform with those from similar studies. ■

Dry weight loss, damaged grains, and number of *S. cerealella* adults that emerged in storage of rice varieties in Pakistan.^a

Variety	Dry wt lost (%)	Damaged grains (%)	Adults that emerged (no.)
DR82	6.1 a	14.1 b	21 bc
KS282	6.3 a	12.9 a	13 a
Lateefy	7.3 b	14.4 c	17 ab
DR83	13.3 c	14.5 c	24 cd
IR6	15.8 d	15.2 d	38 e
Bas 370	20.5 c	16.3 e	38 e
K. Bas	22.6 f	15.1 d	39 e
JP5	25.4 g	20.1 f	59 f

^a In a column, means with the same letter are not significantly different from each other at the 1% level by DMRT.